

PROSPECTIVE DIRECTIONS OF TOURISM PRODUCT DIVERSIFICATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation.

The article is devoted to the issue of diversification of the tourist product in the digital economy.

Key words.

tourism, tourism product, diversification digital economy, strategic sector, tourist and recreational services, packaged tours

In the conditions of the rapid development of interstate integration processes and the current globalization of the world economy, tourism is rapidly developing as a leading strategic field of the world. After all, according to the data of the World Tourism Organization, in 2019, 330 million jobs in the world economy and 10.3% of the total world gross domestic product and 28.3% of the export of services fell on the tourism sector. The World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) in collaboration with Oxford Economics conducted a study on the main trends of the impact of tourism on the world economy in 2023.

According to the report, the global tourism sector is worth \$9.5 trillion this year, which is only 5% less than the pre-pandemic level of 2019, when international travel reached a historic peak.

According to WTTC estimates, despite economic and geopolitical challenges, the recovery of the travel and tourism sector continued at a high pace last year and amounted to 7.7 trillion dollars, up 22% compared to last year. This accounted for 7.6% of the global economy in 2022, the highest contribution from the tourism sector since 2019. However, the contribution of the tourism industry to the world GDP remains 22.9% lower than four years ago²⁵⁷.

For this reason, not only the countries of the world, but also in Uzbekistan today, innovative modernization and diversification of the tourism sector, especially the creation of attractive tourist products and the scientific-theoretical and methodological foundations of sustainable development of tourism, as well as

²⁵⁷ <https://www.rustourismnews.com/2023/05/05/world-tourism-will-recover-by-95-in-2023>

the improvement of the methods of evaluating and increasing the tourist potential, a practical point of view from the point of view, it is of priority to carry out scientific research in the directions of increasing the flow of foreign and domestic tourists, increasing the attractiveness and competitiveness of the industry, and forming a comprehensive system that ensures the export of tourism to the world market as a profitable sector of the economy.

Therefore, the 28th goal of the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 is "To increase the export volume of the republic to 30 billion US dollars in 2026 by increasing the export potential of the republic, in particular, the export of tourism, transport, information and communication, including software and other services 1, Increase by 7 times or bring it to 4.3 billion US dollars" Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. PF-60 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" ²⁵⁸, as well as in the President's appeals to the Oliy Majlis "...in 2025, the number of foreign tourists visiting our country should be increased to 7 million, and the annual income from tourism²⁵⁹ exports to 2 billion dollars" and "...turning tourism into a strategic branch²⁶⁰ of the economy is a priority for us..." Sh.M. Mirziyoev. From national revival to national rise. "Rapid development of tourism, more complete and effective use of the existing huge tourism potential, together with traditional cultural and historical tourism, other potential types of tourism - pilgrimage, ecological, educational, ethnographic, gastronomic, sports, treatment-health, rural, industrial, business tourism and other types, strengthening the social importance of tourism due to the development of children, teenagers and youth tourism, family tourism, social tourism for the elderly" has been defined as one of the goals and priorities of the state policy in the field of tourism in the medium term in our country²⁶¹ [. Therefore, development of new tourist routes, development of types of active tourism, diversification of tourist products by effective use of existing tourist potential and thus sustainable development of tourism are important tasks in this area.

Tourism product diversification is the process of expanding and improving the range of tourism services provided in a particular territory or region. This strategy allows you to increase the attractiveness of the tourism product, diversify

²⁵⁸ <https://lex.uz/docs/5841063>

²⁵⁹ <https://www.gov.uz/uz/news/view/20242>

²⁶⁰ http://ferlibrary.uz/f/shmirziyoyev_4_tom.pdf requires large-scale in-depth scientific research.

²⁶¹ President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev's Decree No. PF-4861 of December 2, 2016 "On measures to ensure rapid development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan". // www.lex.uz

it and ensure the most complete satisfaction of the needs of various categories of potential customers.

Tourism product diversification is the process of expanding and improving the range of tourism services provided in a particular territory or region. This strategy allows you to increase the attractiveness of the tourism product, diversify it and ensure the most complete satisfaction of the needs of various categories of potential customers.

The development of the digital economy dictates new trends in the development of the tourism market in Uzbekistan. In particular, the globalization of the tourism business, the active development and influence of Internet resources on the tourism market, the personification of the approach to organizing travel in a new way forms the development of the tourism market in Uzbekistan. The online travel market is the fastest growing sector of e-commerce in services. In recent years, foreign tourists have been using the Internet to plan and organize their trips around Uzbekistan. In the tourist environment, work is underway to promote dynamic package tours to the market. This is a new technology for the formation and sale of a tourist product by direct access to the resource systems of airlines, hotels and travel service aggregators

The experience of European and Asian tourism organizations shows that in the near future dynamic bundling will become the technological basis for a new strategy for the development of the global tourism industry. In 2022, a total of 5.2 million tourists from foreign countries visited Uzbekistan. This is almost 3 times more than the figure of 2021 (1.8 million people).

In particular, a total of 4,364,800 tourists visited neighboring countries last year, which is 283% more than in 2021. Also, 606,400 tourists from the Commonwealth of Independent States (291% more than in 2021) and 261,600 tourists from foreign countries (198% more than in 2021) came to our country.

Including 75.5 thousand from Turkey (171% more than in 2021), 19.9 thousand from South Korea (347% more than in 2021), 17.7 thousand from Germany (257% more than in 2021), 13.1 thousand from the USA (242% more than in 2021), 11 thousand from France (372% more than in 2021) and 10.5 thousand from Great Britain (264% more than in 2021) visited our country.

It should be noted that in 2022, 49.6 percent of the tourists who came to our country, i.e. 2,593,400 people, were people aged 31 to 55 years. Also, 723,300 foreign tourists were under 18 years old, 846,500 people were between 19 and 30 years old, and 1,069,600 people were over 50 years old.

Approximately 7 million foreign tourists are expected to visit Uzbekistan in 2023²⁶².

Thus, in order to coordinate activities in the field of tourism development in the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is proposed to carry out the following series of activities:

1. It is necessary to coordinate the activities of regional authorities to develop tourism development programs in the Republic 2. Monitor the tourist and recreational potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan and identify opportunities for tourism development, taking into account the recreational capacity of the territories.

2. It is necessary to develop a marketing strategy for the development of tourism in the Republic, which will represent a system of scenarios for achieving the competitive advantages of the territory using modern communication technologies and tools

3. For each region of Uzbekistan, it is required to develop a separate package of proposals for the development of various types of tourism.

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²⁶² <https://aniq.uz/yangilikar/uzbekistonga-tashrif-buyurgan-aksariyat-sayyohlarning-yoshi-31-55-yoshni-tashkil-qildi-foto>]